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Amity University, Lucknow Campus, Malhaur (Near Railway Station), Post Office: Chinhut, Lucknow (UP) - 226028
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Critical Analysis of Gender Issues in Standard VII Textbook of GSBST

H. S. Mistry*

S. C. Panigrahi**

Jayaprada Reddy***

According to National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005) and Dash (2006), the objectives of teaching Social Science is to develop different values, development of human relationships, development for social competence and sense of belongingness should be develop in students. From the concept in a manner that was significantly different from past representations of women and girls? For seeking answer to this question, the authors of this paper critically analysed standard VIII Social Science textbook prescribed by GSBST. The main reason behind selecting standard VIII was because after this stage, students complete their primary education and will enter into secondary level education so during the elementary level the values and knowledge they gain from the texts of Social Science textbook will develop the human values and sense of belongingness as per the objective of social science. The literatures related to Social Science textbooks, gender reflection in textbooks, sexist elements in textbooks and women elements in textbooks failed to answer some of the questions like how teacher interpret the test and pass it to the students by connecting it in the present scenario? Do students is aware about the gender sensitivity given in the social science textbook? The present paper highlights to answer this questions through critically analysis of the gender issues in standard VIII Social Science textbook.

Key words: Gender issues, Standard VIII, Social Science, Textbook, Critical analysis

Introduction

In many societies, places of women and men are unequally at different levels of social organization. From the macro level of the societal economy, through the institutions of society, to small groups and the individual, women and men are differently placed and differently rewarded. In other words, social organization is gendered. We are living in the modern era of change and global connectivity. However, human beings are still discriminated on the basis of religion, race, socio-economic status, cultural background, language, and gender. Although there is a lot of technological development but the mind-set of the society is not significantly changed. Gender discrimination and segregation are the parts of our social mentality. For that reason, struggle for gender equity and gender equality is not very new in our society. Since education is a social progression so, it represents the norms and culture of the society.

Likewise, educational policies, curriculum, and textbooks; mirrors the gender perceptions of the society. Textbook is the most common and widely used tool for teaching learning process.

Teachers have strong belief in the authenticity of the constitution of India has conferred on all Indians, the right to equality as a fundamental right. All Indians are equal before the law (Article 14), no one can be discriminated against by the state on the grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth (article 15(1)), and all Indians are guaranteed equality of opportunity in matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the state (Article 16). The Constitution directs the state to secure equality for men and women, the right to an adequate means of livelihood, equal pay for equal work (Article 39(a) and (d)), just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief (Article 42). In fact, the constitution directs the state to make special provisions in favour of women (also children) (Article 83-15(3)) and to promote harmony and to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women (Article 51-A (e)) (Sen & Kumar, 2001). In addition to this constitutional provision for the equal treatment of women, the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments have provided reservation of 33 percent seats for women in the panchayats and municipalities, to promote their

* UGC-Dr. S. Raddhakrishnan Post-Doctoral Fellow, The M. S. University of Baroda
** Head Department of Education the M. S. University of Baroda
*** M. Ed. Student, Department of Education (CASE) The M. S. University of Baroda

political participation. Despite the existence of these constitutional guarantees and the fundamental right to equality, there are wide disparities between men and women in India in terms of important human development indicators such as education, economic and political participation and health. The wide disparities in education economic and political participation and health are the manifestation of the discrimination against women, which has been practiced from centuries

According to National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005) and Dash (2006) the objective of teaching Social Science is to develop different values, development of human relationship, development for social competence and sense of belongingness should be develop in students. From the concept of gender biasness and the role of textbooks, the question emerges that did gender get portrayed in a manner that was significantly different from past representations of women and girls? Investigators selected standard VIII because in this stage students will be completing the primary level and will enter into secondary so at this level the values and knowledge they gain from the texts of Social Science textbook will develop the human values and sense of belongingness as per the objective of social science. From the review of literatures related to Social Science textbooks, gender reflection in textbooks, sexist elements in textbook and women elements in textbooks, it was observed that some questions still remained unanswered which needs to be answered. The questions are: How teacher interpret the text and pass it to the students by connecting it in the present scenario? Do Students is aware about the gender sensitivity given in the Social Science Textbook? Through the attempt of the present study, investigators had tried to answer these questions.

Statement of the Problem

Critical analysis of gender issues in standard VIII social science textbook of GSBST

Objectives of the Study

- To study the Gender issues in the present textbook of standard VIII Social Science.
- To find out the negative and positive aspect of gender issues in standard VIII Social Science textbook.
- To study the opinion of teachers regarding Gender issues in Social Science textbook.
- To study the awareness of students about the Gender issues.

Explanation of the Terms Used

Gender Issues: In the present study, gender issues are that influence one sex more than the other. The relationship similarities and differences on the changing aspirations, roles, contributions and status of man and women also considered as gender issues for the present study.

Critical Analysis: In the present study, critical analysis is subjective writing because it expresses the writer's opinion or evaluation of a text. Questions to critically analyse the contents from Social Science textbook were what is said? Why is it so? What else could have been done? What is the positive and negative aspect of it?

Delimitation of the Study

- The present study was delimited to analyse Social Science textbook of standard VIII for the academic year 2013-2014.
- Further the study was delimited to English medium schools of Vadodara city affiliated to Gujarat State Education Board, Gujarat.

Methodology of the Study

Research Design: Descriptive Survey was used for the present study.

Population: All the teachers teaching Social Science at upper primary level and standard VIII students studying in the English medium schools of Vadodara city affiliated to Gujarat State Education Board, Gujarat, were considered as the population for the present study.

Sample: 10 Upper Primary English medium schools of Vadodara city were selected randomly by using lottery method. The teachers teaching Social Science at Upper Primary level of the selected 10 English medium schools were selected as the sample of teachers. Thus, the sample size of the teachers was 10. For the sample of standard VIII students, 10 students (5 boys and 5 girls) were selected randomly from each school. Thus the sample size of the students was 100 (50 boys and 50 girls).

Tools and Techniques

The following tools and techniques have been employed in the study

- Content Analysis Sheet: The content analysis sheet was prepared with considering academic aspect covered in standard VIII English medium Social Science textbook. Textual

- analysis was done on physical and content aspects, and authors of textbook
- Opinionnaire for Primary School Social Science teachers: Opinionnaire scale was prepared for the teachers teaching Social Science in standard VIII in terms to know their views and suggestions on gender issues reflected in standard VIII Social Science textbook.
- Observation: Unstructured observation was done with covering the observation of classroom teaching-learning, teacher-students interaction and teacher's behaviour with boy and girl students. Though the observation was unstructured, the investigators broadly focused on the observation of teacher's attitude towards boy and girl students, attention to boy and girl students, assigning roles, tasks, duties and responsibility to boy and girl students, evaluation of boy and girl students, segregation and interaction
- with boy and girl students, gender issues and bias based illustrations.
- Interview Schedule for Standard VIII Students: Unstructured interview was conducted with the standard VIII students to know their views on gender issues and gender awareness.
- The investigators had been critically analyzed English medium standard VIII Social Science textbooks of two semesters from the point of view of gender issues. The opinions of teachers teaching Social Science at Upper Primary level about the gender issues were collected personally by using opinionnaire. Data pertaining to the standard VIII students' views on gender issues were collected through the un-structured interview.
- The data were analysed by using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. The data collected through the observation and interview and open-ended items of opinionnaire were analysed through the content analysis whereas, for the close-ended items of opinionnaire, frequency and percentage were counted.
- Major Findings
 - Male dominated contents were found on the cover pages of the standard VIII Social Science textbook of both the semester. Both semester books were having total 3 male dominant
 - No references of Vijaya Laxmi Pandit related to Azad Hind Fauj is given in textbook.
 - No women participation in freedom movement reflected in Social Science textbook.
 - No reference of percentage reserved for women in Rajyasabha is given.
 - More importance given to the male revolutionaries of India.
 - No any information about female judges.
 - Explanation limited to only male leaders.
 - Religious leader constraints only to the male leaders.
 - Only four female reformers i.e. Sarojini Naidu, Vijayalaxmi Pandit, Rani Laxmibai and Madam Cama works included.
 - More importance given to only Gandhi ji while his wife Kasturba Gandhi's role neglected.
 - Framing of male characters only.
 - No mention of female reformer.
 - Less importance given to the female in standard VIII Social Science textbooks such as:
 - 111 male role models included and only 15 female role models included in both semesters Social Science textbook.
 - 70 male dominated pictures were found in standard VIII social science textbook while only 6 pictures were female dominated.
 - From the content analysis of 16 lessons of the Social Science textbook of standard VIII, it was found that majority of the lessons were of male dominated due to male dominant words and sentences, presentation of stereotyped roles of both male or female characters and over emphasis on male characters.
 - Overall, 4 lessons reflected male dominated titles whereas 12 lessons were related to gender neutral titles. No one lesson was found related to female dominate.
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 - No mention of female reformer.
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 - Only four female reformers i.e. Sarojini Naidu, Vijayalaxmi Pandit, Rani Laxmibai and Madam Cama works included.
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Data Analysis

The data were analysed by using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. The data collected through the observation and interview and open-ended items of opinionnaire were analysed through the content analysis whereas, for the close-ended items of opinionnaire, frequency and percentage were counted.

Data Collection

- Opinionnaire for Primary School Social Science teachers: Opinionnaire scale was prepared for the teachers teaching Social Science in standard VIII in terms to know their views and suggestions on gender issues reflected in standard VIII Social Science textbook.
- Observation: Unstructured observation was done with covering the observation of classroom teaching-learning, teacher-students interaction and teacher's behaviour with boy and girl students. Though the observation was unstructured, the investigators broadly focused on the observation of teacher's attitude towards boy and girl students, attention to boy and girl students, assigning roles, tasks, duties and responsibility to boy and girl students, evaluation of boy and girl students, segregation and interaction
- with boy and girl students, gender issues and bias based illustrations.
- Interview Schedule for Standard VIII Students: Unstructured interview was conducted with the standard VIII students to know their views on gender issues and gender awareness.

- No single example given related to the cases of women harassment right
 - No mention about the Durga bhabi, one of revolutionary in India.
 - A female standing beside Gandhi Ji given in the picture but name or any detail about that female not given anywhere in the text (Pg.no. 78 & 79).
 - Latest problem of women safety not mentioned anywhere in textbook.
 - No mention about the female member in constitution.
 - Name of the females contributed in Dandi March not given in the textbook.
- Representation of women in the panels of architects of Social Science Textbooks of standard VIII was very low, with less than a third of them being women.
 - Standard VIII Students' Views On Gender Issues
 - The students interviewed felt that gender bias prevailed in the education system.
 - A large number of the students felt gender issues as a major problem for schools and Social Science textbooks of standard VIII are gender biased.
 - The majority of the students felt that parents generally prefer their male child.
 - Majority of the students felt that teachers flavoured the male gender while encouraging students for different professions, solving difficulties and illustrating the portraits of eminent figures, teachers favoured girls but according to the situation of the responses of the girl students.
 - The majority of the students liked female teachers.
 - Students are aware of gender sensitivity given in Social Science textbook.
 - Teachers' Opinion On Gender Issues Standard VIII Social Science Textbook
 - All the ten (100%) teachers opined that the men and women could treated with the same respect, dignity and seriousness; proper linguistic expressions use.
 - All the ten (100%) teachers opined that secularism could be made to achieve educational objectives.
 - 80% teachers opined that the textbook could reject the traditional value of dependence of women on men.
 - All the ten (100%) teachers opined that the emphasizing the process of decision making to be shared by both the sexes at all levels.
 - 80% teachers opined that more female role models in Social Science textbooks could be included and unnecessary gender pronouns could be avoided and these being recast.

Discussion

The findings confirmed that males are more visible than females in text and pictures of the standard VIII Social Science textbooks. The females' low visibility in texts and pictures could be the result of writer's wrong ideology and belief about women due to their physical or psychological nature. Accordingly, the investigators assume that the writers avoided depicting women as determining personalities; consequently, they excluded them from mainstream society and refrained from endowing women their right to be presented. Women's limited roles may also have causal association with the writers' culture. A culture embodies and sustains social values attached to male or female and it shapes peoples' expectations about what types of role women and men have to do. One other possible reason could be the limited women occupation may be ascribed to gender stereotypes. By this we mean the negative cliché and attitude based on untrue ideas that have been around us for thousands of years. Women tend to be stereotyped in a limited series of roles. However today these clichés are obsolete gender stereotypes. Today, everyone knows that girls do not have to be housewives only but can be corporate leaders or fire-fighters, while men can nurture babies without shame. The writers of the textbooks have presented females having limited roles because they may have influenced by these baseless clichés. Gender stereotypes are dangerous for people who are the target of these stereotypes because they can change peoples' destiny. If females believe them, they may become a nurse or tailor and they may be deprived of becoming a fire-fighter or a miner. The most satisfactory solution to the problem may be a critical pedagogy after all, a pedagogy informed by critical social theory that seeks to understand and critique the historical and socio-political context of schooling, but also the wider society (Pennycook, 1990).

negative attitudes toward different groups of people, i.e., women, children, the old, the disabled and so on (Gract, 1989). This study supports the findings of the result of students that reveals less visibility of females both in text and pictures, and males' role is more represented than female role by the textbooks.

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Suggestions

1. Curriculum development, textbooks, teaching and learning support materials need to take into account the pro-active role that women play in nation building.
2. Social Science teachers need to re-think their pedagogical, teaching styles and attitudes; and ensure that these promote gender equality.
3. There is need to edit Social Science textbooks across all the levels of schooling to remove stereotypical content, images and pictures which reinforce gender stereotyping.
4. Syllabus designers are advised to keep a balance between male and female character, roles and frequency of male and female pictures.

Conclusion

The present study was carried with the intention of finding gender issues embedded in the Social Science Textbook of standard VIII and its transaction in classrooms. On analysing the content of Textbooks and observing their transaction, it was found that every aspect of the textbooks and its transaction were dominated by the male gender. Women were not given adequate representation in the textbooks architects. Though the titles of the majority of lessons of the Social Science textbook of standard VIII are gender neutral, among the rest, nearly all lessons had titles that had the male domination. Majority of the lessons of the Social Science textbooks have more number of words and sentences that showed the domination of men. Again a large number of pictorial representations provided in the textbooks to great extent are being dominated by the male. Some education experts claim that textbooks as part of the curriculum are replete with different kinds of discrimination and